

Kinetic Sound Sculpture: "Sounding Influencer" a new Instrument with moving loudspeakers – further development of the underlying pendulum model

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ABSTRACT

The kinetic sound sculpture Sounding Influencer emerged from a long sequence of developments. We developed a computer simulation in which 12 moving loudspeakers with their sound changes could be made audible and which made possible the planning of a musical sequence and a choreography intended for three dancers.

Due to the limitations imposed by Corona, it was not possible to work with dancers. We instead transferred the principle of the 12 moving loudspeakers to a construction with 12 pendulums that can be pulled into a horizontal position again and again with the help of motors and then be released at a precise moment to swing freely. The realization presented a great challenge, especially technically.

The effects provoked by the swinging pendulums are on the one hand predictable, but on the other hand also unforeseeable, speculative and surprising, always depending on the location in which the construction is placed.

The result is an instrument that was tested with first composition and presented for three days at "FAIart"¹ fair in Schaffhausen. The technical development is explained in detail. The theory of sound change with oscillating sound sources is expanded based on the sound results of the first presentations.

1. INTRODUCTION

Moving loudspeakers have been used in various musical contexts since the 1940s [1]. Since 2018, the course *Composing with and for Moving Loudspeakers*² at the Zurich University of the Arts (ZHdK) has been continuously producing works in which moving loudspeakers are used.

The work presented here was intended to continue a development in order to find better solutions for fast horizontal and vertical loudspeaker movements. Initially, a project with three dancers wearing a loudspeaker on each limb was envisioned, allowing to perform fast movements of sounds in all three spatial directions. Due to performance restrictions imposed by Covid 19 regulations, the composition

¹ Female Artist Table.

² <https://blog.zhdk.ch/soundinmotion/>

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could not be realized with dancers. Instead, the kinetic sound sculpture *Sounding Influencer* was created.

Working with speakers attached to pendulums has already been developed by Capeche [2], Escobar [3], Szram [4], Cornford[5], Leper [6], Beutter [7], Schilliger [8] and others.

The sculpture *Sounding Influencer* consists of a construction with 12 swinging pendulums, sensors and motors that enable the pendulums to be lifted and swung out horizontally. Each pendulum holds a loudspeaker.

In order to develop the composition before the completion of the kinetic sound sculpture itself, a pendulum simulation program was constructed in MaxMSP and JavaScript. Substituting pendulums for the dancers reduced the speakers' freedom of movement to the reciprocating motion. The duration of the attenuating oscillations of the moving speakers depends on the oscillation length and maximum of deflection. We chose a pendulum length of 2.05 meters. To initiate the oscillation the pendulum is elevated by 90 degrees on to the horizontal plane. In this combination the decay process lasts two to three minutes depending on the number of swinging pendulums.

Composition No. 1 *Decelerating Floatation*, which was realized with the kinetic sound sculpture *Sounding Influencer*, is explained below in part 3. The research interest associated with this work concerns the question: What do I hear in different dynamic interactions between different moving sine tones? How is the dynamic interaction additionally influenced by the surrounding space and the subjective intention of the listener?

2. THEORY OF SOUND CHANGE WITH OSCILLATING SOUND SOURCE

2.1 Doppler Effect and Period

With a swinging pendulum, a frequency change occurs according to the Doppler [9, 10] law: If the pendulum swings towards the listener, the pitch becomes higher; if it swings back, the pitch becomes lower. It reaches its maximum speed and the resulting greatest pitch change in the zero position (rest position).

$$f_a = \frac{f_s}{1 \pm \frac{v_s}{c}} \quad (1)$$

f_a : Apparent Frequency, f_s : True Frequency of source, v_s : Velocity of source, c : Speed of sound (343 m/s).

The pendulum reaches a maximum speed of 6.27 m/s in the first period. After 1'19" the maximum speed is only 1.98 m/s.

$$T = 2\pi\sqrt{\frac{J}{lmg \cdot 1.18}} \Rightarrow f_p = \frac{1}{T} \quad (2)$$

Period of oscillation of a physical pendulum: *J*: Moment of inertia, *l*: Length of the pendulum, *m*: Mass of the pendulum, *g*: Gravity (9.81 m/s²), *f_p*: Frequency of pendulum.

For *J* = 3.267 Kg m², *l* = 2.05 meters, *m* = 0.9 Kg ⇒ *T* = 2.90 seconds, *f_p* = 0.34 Hz.

2.2 Pendulum simulation program

The model for the simulation of the pitch shift of a pendulum consists of a sine tone generator. The movement of the virtual pendulum is calculated with the mathematical equation of a Simple Pendulum. From this, the distance to a virtual listener is calculated to determine the instantaneous length of a variable delay through which the sine tone is passed. There is such a simulation for each of the 12 pendulums.

3. COMPOSITION

For Composition No. 1 *Decelerating Floatation*, 12 sine tones between F4 and E5 were arranged in a particular way based on A4 = 432 Hz resulting in three tetrachords of the same structure:

T1: F4 – G4 – F#4– G#4

T2: A4 – B4 – A#4– C5

T3: C#5– D#5– D5 – E5

In this sequence every whole step is followed by a half step, and every half step is followed by a whole step. The direction of the whole steps is always upwards. The direction of the half steps alternates between up and down and down and up, respectively. Every tetrachord consists of two whole steps and one half step. The direction of the half step in the tetrachord is always downwards. Between the tetrachords, there is always a half step upwards.

Figure 1. Scale. Blue: Whole step; red: Half step.

The whole composition is an arrangement of decay processes of a single moving loudspeaker or a combination of moving loudspeakers. If there is a combination of moving loudspeakers the swing-out process is organized either in parallel or in opposite directions.

The composition starts with the first sine tone of the first pendulum F4. The pitch shift is very strong in the beginning, corresponding to the fast and extensive movement of the loudspeaker at the begin of the decay process. After a while the pitch shift becomes more subtle, remaining nevertheless very noticeable. A sensor evaluates the decay process.

When the pendulum movement falls under a defined cut-off, the next step of the composition starts. Here two sine

tones F4 and A4 move upwards in the horizontal plane. The decay process of both pendulums is organized in the opposite manner. The second pendulum starts its swing-out process when the first pendulum has almost reached the opposite horizontal point of return. Now the pitch shift of two sine tones is heard together, which implicates a permanent changing of the audible interval. The initial range oscillates between a minor third and a fourth around the estimated interval of major third. The interval range narrows over time, but the variation is nevertheless very well audible.

The next combination of moving loudspeakers includes the sine tones F4, A4 and C#5. Again, all three pendulums are moved upwards in the horizontal plane. Pendulums one and two start the decay process together. Pendulum three again starts its swing-out process when the other two pendulums have almost reached the opposite horizontal points of return. Now we can hear variations around the estimated excessive chord consisting of two major thirds. In the next steps, three more pendulums are successively introduced (G4, B4, D#5), so that gradually, the complete whole tone series is heard.

In addition to dynamic and acoustic interactions, the variations of parallel and counter-rotating pendulum movements create interesting visual combinations that are deliberately used in this composition, such as in sequence 9. Here the impression is created that the pendulums reflect leg movements, i.e., people striding in step, although slight deviations occur.

The composition consists of 42 sequences, with a total duration of about 2 h 15 min. The beginning and end are designed in such a way that looping is also possible.

Figure 2. The 42 steps of the Composition No. 1. Green boxes: Pendulums in phase (0°). Red boxes: Pendulums out of phase (180°).

4. SYSTEM STRUCTURE

The kinetic sound sculpture *Sounding Influencer* consists of five main components:

4.1 Pendulum: Loudspeaker, electromagnet, rotary sensor

Each pendulum consists of a 2.05-meter-long aluminum tube with a diameter of 18 mm. At one end there is a bracket that holds the loudspeaker and the electromagnet and connects them to the tube in a torsion-proof way.

The loudspeaker chassis is used open. As a dipole, it radiates the sound both to the front and to the rear, while there is strong damping in the lateral direction.

Figure 3. System Overview.

The electromagnet is so strong that the pendulum is lifted even if only part of the plate is in contact with the magnet.

The rotary sensor is attached to the axis of the pendulum and continuously measures the pendulum's deflection.

4.2 Drive motors, motor boxes

Stepper motors with an integrated control and a built-in encoder were chosen. The encoder determines the absolute position of the axis and thanks to its high resolution (200 full steps with 256 micro-steps each) it can be positioned very precisely.

The integrated control simplifies the control of the motor. Two commands (up/down) are sufficient to move the metal plate to the lower (at the pendulum) or upper position (release point of the pendulum).

The motor is mounted in a bracket that also integrates the rope winder. This sits directly on the motor shaft.

To supply the motors with power and to tap the control line with RS-485, connected in series, six identical motor boxes were constructed.

4.3 Control box: serial interface, Arduino board, relay

The motors are controlled through the RS-485 serial interface. The latter is connected to the control computer via USB and to the motors via a two-wire cable in.

The Arduino board receives the data from the rotary sensors, calculates the current angle of the pendulums and whether they are active or still and transmits both to the control computer. It serves also as controller for switching on and off the relays for the electromagnets. Since 24 analogue connections are needed, the Arduino board Mega 2560 was used.

The relays are used to switch on and off the electromagnets (24V/0.4A each magnet).

4.4 Control unit: MacPro, central control software, sound generation

MaxMSP runs on the MacPro control computer. It fulfills six tasks:

1. Tapping the sensor data that is supplied by the Arduino via OSC.

2. Calibrating and controlling the motors: the upper and lower positions to which the motors move the iron plates must be determined. These values are stored in the motors' memory.

3. Switching the electromagnets on and off.

4. Sound generation: In this version only 12 sine tones are played. It is of course possible to use other types of vibration.

5. Playing the score: This is a list into which is entered per line which pendulums are swinging and whether they are triggered in the same or opposite phase. The programme mutes pendulums that are not active and ramps up the volume of those that are set in motion.

6. Web server for listening to the pendulums via mobile devices when the pendulums are muted. The mobile devices log on to the server via a website. The sound synthesis capabilities of modern web browsers are used: 12 sine tone generators are started on the mobile device, the volume and pitch of which are controlled from the server. The control data is calculated directly from the pendulum movement, i.e., the Doppler shift is calculated from the current speed and the deviation from the target pitch. The model is not yet very sophisticated and can only inadequately convey the frequency modulation heard in space.

4.5 Audio section: USB MADI interface, DA converter, 12-channel amplifier.

A MADI-Interface serves as the audio interface. The MADI signal is converted in an DA converter and fed to the speakers via a 12-channel amplifier.

5. SETUP UP ON SITE

On the *FATart* fair, two trusses and four tripods were used to set up the kinetic sound sculpture at the exhibition site: The motors were attached to the rear one, and the pendulums hung from the front one. The distance between the pendulums in that version was 0.6 meters, so the total width was 9 meters (including tripods).

Figure 4. *Sounding Influencer*, setup on the *FATart* fair.

6. RESULTS

The first presentation of *Sounding Influencer* took place at *FATart* fair in Schaffhausen, Switzerland in 2020. On the one hand there was a sound installation of the whole composition *Decelerating Floatation* playing in a loop and two distinct performances with short excerpts of the composition. On the other hand interested persons could stream

the audio sound while the installation took place without live sounds from the loudspeakers.

Apart from the sound design, the aesthetic appearance of the movements of the pendulums and the activity of the slices and motors also had a great impact on the overall experience. Listeners also observed with interest the changes of the combinations of pendulums. The additional visual impressions with the moving metal disks that were introduced out of technical considerations and their clacking when they docked on the speakers gave the sound installation an additional, unexpected charm.

Amazingly, the auditory impression of a single moving sinusoid is completely different from that of an immobile sound source. The sound appears lively and constantly changing. The combination of two or more sine tones also sounds completely different on moving and static sound sources. The permanent change in pitch due to the Doppler effect adds an iridescent or shimmering quality to the sound.

However, there are strong differences in the listening experience when one compares the moving tones that come from the loudspeaker with the streamed tones heard through headphones. The streamed sound was related to the real velocity of the pendulum and sounds much more mechanical. The room acoustics are an important factor completely missing from the listening experience when streaming. To better understand the influence of room acoustics on the actual listening experience, we made a sound recording, which is described in the following sections.

6.1 Analysis of the perceived sound

6.1.1 Recording setup

Figure 5. Recording setup. Microphone (M) at audience position.

The recording was made at our *Labor* with a Neumann KM184 microphone. The *Labor* measures 7.58 m x 7.59 m x 5.77 m (w x l x h).

6.1.2 Frequency modulation

Figure 6 shows (next to the amplitude) the sonogram of the 1st period (A-E-A) of sequence 1 (see Figure 2). One oscillation period lasts approximately 2.9 seconds, the maximum velocity is about 6.2 m/s. The fundamental pitch is 370.0 Hz, the maximum and minimum pitch change is: ± 6.7 Hz.

When the loudspeaker moves towards the microphone, the pitch rises according to the Doppler effect law. The pendulum reaches its highest speed and thus the highest pitch in the rest position (B). As it continues to move towards the microphone, the pitch drops back to the original

value as the speed decreases to 0 m/s at the turning point in front of the microphone (E). When the pendulum swings back again, it moves away from the microphone, causing the pitch to drop. Again, it passes through the rest position (B') at maximum speed, where the lowest pitch is reached, which then rises to the original value when decelerating to 0 m/s.

Surprising is the fact that in the recording not only one pitch change occurs during the movement of a pendulum, which is to be expected, but also a second modulation opposite (lower course). These are early reflections that are almost as strong as the direct sound and modulate the sine wave once again. Their pitch change is almost inverse to the pitch change of the direct sound.

Figure 6. Amplitude and sonogram (1st period). Dark line: Amplitude. Below: Frequency. X-axis: Time, Y-axis: Amplitude (dB) and frequency (350 – 390 Hz).

6.1.3 Amplitude modulation

Just before the swinging loudspeaker reaches the microphone (E), the amplitude rises to its maximum (C), then drops rapidly by almost 20 dB (D). On the last few centimeters to the turning point (E), the amplitude again rises by 10 dB. When swinging back, the amplitude curve is almost the same and mirrored: Falling to the minimum amplitude (D'), rising to the maximum (C') and reaching the same loudness value in the starting point (A) as before.

With a swinging pendulum, the amplitude is a function of the distance of the loudspeaker to the microphone: the closer the loudspeaker is, the louder it sounds. In principle, this curve can be recognized from the measurement in Figure 6. However, wave-shaped smaller and larger amplitude fluctuations are superimposed over it.

These are beatings resulting from the superposition of the direct sound with the early reflections. They are constantly changing because, due to the movement of the pendulum, the radiation position of the loudspeaker in relation to the floor and the walls changes permanently. The beatings are especially numerous when the pendulum moves around the rest point (B and B' respectively), as this is where it is closest to the floor. Due to the fast movement of the pendulum close to the ground, many beatings occur.

The amplitude increase towards (C) occurs because of the proximity to the microphone. However, it is greater than in (E), where the loudspeaker is closest to the microphone. Here one would expect a higher level, it is, however, almost the same as in (A) where the loudspeaker is furthest away.

The drop after (C), the rise after (D) and drop after (E) are again beatings caused by the superposition of direct sound and the early reflections. The slowing down and acceleration of the pendulum give them this pronounced course.

6.1.4 frequency and amplitude modulation with increasing time

As Figure 7 shows, the deflection of the pendulum after 1'19" seconds is only about 10%. One period lasts 2.74 seconds - the pendulum now has a slightly higher oscillation frequency, while the maximum speed is only 1.19 m/s.

The amplitude differences are smaller, but still amount to approximately 6 dB. The distance to the microphone changes only slightly, basically leading to a balanced amplitude. Nevertheless, two additional increases or decreases around (B) and (B') can be seen. These are again caused by the superposition of the direct sound and the early reflections. Since the pendulum only moves slowly, these beatings proceed slowly.

One can perceive these two amplitude peaks very clearly, however. The change in pitch, on the other hand, which is no more than about 1.4 Hz, is so small that it is at best perceived as a change in timbre.

In the sonogram, the frequency of the direct sound is clearly visible, those of the early reflections are only vaguely recognizable.

Figure 7. Amplitude and sonogram, 1 period after 1'19". Dark line: Amplitude. Below: Frequency. X-axis: Time, Y-axis: Amplitude (dB) and frequency (350 – 390 Hz).

6.1.5 Listening experience

The sine tone played through the loudspeaker has a constant pitch (370 hertz) and a constant level. As soon as the pendulum moves even slightly, frequency modulation occurs due to the Doppler effect and amplitude modulations occur due to swinging back and force. The amplitude modulation receives a clearly audible pulsation through the superimposition of direct sound and early reflections. The frequency modulation together with the reflected waves leads to a spread frequency range of up to 14.4 Hz (363.3 – 376.7 Hz), effecting in a sound with multiple modulations that no longer has any resemblance to a motionless sine wave.

The listening experience is very individual. It results from the interaction with personal associations or the individual focus of attention. There are indications that, depending on the subjective focus, differently small melody elements can be picked up out of this dazzling sound. Some persons told us, that the slow changes and repetitive movements or sounds for them had a meditative aspect. At the first presentation, the audience was polarized: for some, the composition had a "pull" effect. They listened very attentively. Some listened for very long periods of time. Others experienced a "repellent effect". The sounds were perceived as disturbing.

The assumption that the pendulums would synchronize when they swing was not confirmed. Rather, the opposite

was the case. Often pendulums started synchronously and would then slowly desynchronize. This is probably due to construction problems e.g., minimal deviations in the axis position. On the other hand, there were also pendulum combinations that remained very stable in their synchronization.

The pendulum movement served as the basis for sound development. As explained in chapter 2, the sound is modulated in frequency and amplitude by the pendulum movement. In addition, the reflections from the back wall and the floor have the greatest influence. The strength of the frequency modulation can be influenced by the speed of the pendulum. The distance to the floor can influence both the amplitude modulation and the comb filter effects. This allows additional modeling of the sound to a certain extent.

Changes take place slowly, they are sometimes hardly perceptible, but never boring.

Interestingly, the speed of the pendulum oscillation did not remain constant over the time of the oscillation, but neither did it slow down, as one might expect. On the contrary: with a steady decrease in the amplitude with which the pendulum swings, the period becomes somewhat shorter. After 1'19", a period of 2.74 s was measured, which increases the frequency to $f_p = 0.36$ Hz. The initial frequency was $f_p = 0.34$ Hz.

7. DISCUSSION AND OUTLOOK

The search for fast loudspeaker movements in the horizontal and vertical planes with the construction of the *Sounding Influencer* not only yielded an interesting sonic result, but also beautiful visual and scenic impressions. As postulated by Grayson [11] in 1975, we were able to achieve an integration of visual form and beauty and magical, musical sounds with the kinetic sound sculpture *Sounding Influencer*. We look forward to *playing* other compositions with this new instrument or to including it in concerts or performances with other instruments or audio-visual arrangements.

The construction worked very well with few failures during the three days of the first exhibition. However, some weaknesses became apparent, which we would like to remedy in a second expansion stage:

The winding of the cord onto the spool by the motor needs to be fundamentally reworked. Sometimes it wound itself unnoticed around the motor axis, after a while causing a sudden failure of the pendulum. To solve this problem, the cord should firstly be wound onto the spool with a reciprocating cord guide, and, secondly must be guided with a counterweight so that it can never become loose, even if the iron plate has already arrived at the pendulum but the motor is still unwinding some more cord.

The motor should be controlled so that the iron plate can also be guided to a more strongly swinging pendulum. In this case, the motor must pull back the string as the pendulum moves towards it. When it moves away, it has to unwind more string. This allows faster contact between the plate and the magnet and thus faster deceleration of the pendulums.

It should be possible to vary the length of the pendulum so that the pendulum speed can be changed. However, the

realization requires some more research work and will be done in a third stage.

In addition to the motor-controlled cord guide for deceleration, each pendulum should have an additional brake to precisely control the period of oscillation of the respective pendulum. It has been found that the swinging out of a pendulum can take up to five minutes. This is very long, preventing rapid action.

The detection of the second pitch line, which represent the reflections is in line with the results of Stonawski[12]. They did not describe any beatings however, they did not investigate sine tones either, but rather noises such as a car engine or human footsteps.

In our pendulum simulation, neither these reflections nor the beatings caused when passing close to the ground are taken into account. Therefore, it sounds artificial and less interesting. Inserting the frequency response of these reflections already greatly enriches the sound and brings its acoustic quality quite close to the natural sound response of the pendulum. With the simulation of the beats close to the ground, the pendulum simulation will come even closer to the original. This makes it a good tool for preparing a composition when the installation is not accessible. Likewise, the simulation via the web browser will sound better if two oscillators are used for each pendulum instead of only one, which represent the pitch curve of the direct sound and the early reflections. In addition, the amplitude curve must also be taken into account more precisely. For this, the model must include all the necessary parameters, i.e., instantaneous velocity and distance to the floor and the back wall.

8. CONCLUSION

We see the kinetic sound sculpture *Sounding Influencer* as a new kind of instrument that can be used in many different ways. It confirms the thesis that a moving loudspeaker, in contrast to a static one, steps out of its role as a mere sound mediator and becomes an instrument itself. The specific features of this kinetic sound sculpture are the permanently moving sound of each individual tone (amplitude and frequency modulation) and the dynamic interaction of the sounding tones with each other and with the space at any given moment, which would not be possible without loudspeaker movement.

We started with pure sine tones in a chromatic twelve-tone series. Various parameters can be changed to create entirely new sequences: The tone system and the triggering moments can be freely chosen, the oscillation period basically depends on the pendulum length, but can be varied by the braking processes.

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